

Cover Page

DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23>

BEHAVIOURAL STUDY OF STRAY (STREET) DOG'S IN LUCKNOW CITY, UTTAR PRADESH

¹Monika Airy and ²Newton Paul

¹Master of Science in Zoology and ²Assistant Professor

^{1&2}Department of Zoology, Isabella Thoburn College
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Behaviour of a street dogs and it can be easily domesticated as compare to breeds dogs, physical and emotional factors play a very important role in their behaviour, indie dogs also known to be street dogs are seeming as menace in society and a threat due to few unfortunate events of dog bites are sufficient to turn people against stray dogs and perceive them all viciously. In all probability, a dog does not bite unless provoked by someone, sick or in pain. In 1758 Carl Linnaeus gives nomenclature for dogs is Canis, they come from grey wolf species, in 1999 found that domestic dogs evolve from grey wolf, and they were the first species which has been domesticated by humans. They both easily adapted each other behaviour to live with best human- canine bond, because of best companionship they are known as man's best friend. Benefits of owning a dog in both physical and mental cases are beneficiary to humans. The life of street dogs is miserable and people seems them a dirty creature in society. Different locations have been chosen to observe their behavior, food habits, reproductive rate, survival rate, death rate and diseases from they are suffering all has been observed in study. As the study reveals that they are not harmful for society and easily domesticated in the environment we used to live.

Keywords: Behaviour, Street Dogs, Companionship, Humans, Gestures.

Introduction

The behaviour of street dog depends upon various factors most importantly their habitation and feeding habit and makes them easily domesticated by humans. The Swedish zoologist and botanist named Carl Linnaeus in year 1758, the two-word naming of species their binomial nomenclature which is Canis [23]. The domestic dog may evolve from the grey wolf and it is considered that modern grey wolf is the dog's closet living relative. The dogs were the first species which has been domesticated by the humans [24]. Dogs and humans easily adapted each other's behaviour and make a unique bond of human-canine bond. The dogs breeds having various behaviours, physical attributes and sensory capabilities. This positive vibes on human society have given them the name of "man's best friend" [15].

Dogs accomplish several roles in the human community in early period humans, owning dogs for the main purpose of thought to have been use for hunting dexterity and the protection they conferred against other predators in twenty-first century humans, dogs stay to fulfil these roles for humans are companions, confidants, and family member, the dog is a work partner, providing positive atmosphere. The impact of dog and other companion animals in humans' health has been the subject of considerable research since the 1980s.

Owning a dog has countless psychological and physiological benefits however, a behaviour of a dog may understandable itself in a diversity of adverse ways, including aggression. Many Researches proposed that genetics and atmosphere play very important role in aggression and other behaviour of dog. It was confirmed that owners can affect their dogs' behaviour. Owners can unintentionally condition or encourage their dogs to misbehave, where it may happen through their imprecise acuties or misguided actions towards the dogs. Dogs are usually considered friends or family member of the house, with the owner-pet connection appropriate the evolutionary attachment structure of the parent-child bond. Dogs impart safety and wellbeing, provided that companionship and social support, pleasure in recreation and relaxation.

The life of a dog on street is miserable. In our surroundings there is one such dog. It is very dirty. Its body is covered with all over with wounds. They are sometimes bleeding; they are kicked and beaten by humans without any reasons wherever they go. It wanders from house to house to get some crumbs of food for their tough survival they get very little to eat. They starve. It is lean and thin. It barks at the passers-by. Sometimes it gets a good punishment at their hands. They don't get any pat and the love that pet dogs get. They are neglected and uncared by society. In day and night, they are without a shelter; they sleep wherever they find a place to lie. Even in winter they used to sleep in the open area and in hot days of summer, they can be seen lying in a gutter. They live on bones that lie scattered outside a butcher's shop or other dirty things lying in bazars and streets. They dare not move out of its own street. When it goes to other streets, and area its comparable-dogs drive it away. In cities, stray dogs are killed because people think they are a great nuisance. People think they spread diseases, sometimes they turn mad and bite people. Who can love such miserable

Cover Page

DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23>

creatures? In short, a street dog is hated by all in society. They are unwanted and good for-nothing. They are an untouchable. It is contemptible. The poor condition of the dogs in society, most of the dogs are in poor health condition, especially in rural and low economical areas. The street dogs suffer from all sorts of issues ranging from starvation, diseases such as parvo, distemper, rabies, mange, worms and much more than this. Learning more information about street dogs and their behaviour to resolving issues with people free-ranging dogs or street dogs are just as good as any other dogs by using basic human gestures, and that street dogs are as smart as people often imagine [12].

Dogs getting hit by vehicles is one of the biggest reasons for injuries to street dogs, and second people use to beat them for their satisfaction without any reason, while in many shops they see people they think that this human will give them food but no they either get any food insist that they get beaten by stones, people kicked them many more. As said in history dogs are good companion of humans there is no matter whether dogs are street one or breeds one both need love and care.

The Breeds that were developed in India and originate from our country but have been unnoticed so much that are now highly depleted in numbers. Most of these dog breeds are quite unheard of let alone seen by most of the humans in India. The craze for international breeds leading to over-breeding of the popular Western breeds has also resulted in few Indian breeds almost becoming extinct. Certain individuals across the country gradually realised this issue and decided to revive many such dog breeds [1].

Material and Method

Most of the population looks at stray dogs as a menace and a threat due to few unfortunate events of dog bites are sufficient to turn people against stray dogs and perceive them all viciously. In all probability, a dog does not bite unless provoked by someone. Here my work is on “behaviour of a street dog and it can be domesticated”. Therefore, following strategy was made to observe their behaviour. 12 different locations from Lucknow India have been chosen for the behavioural experiment, observation done on Indie dogs, through observing their feeding habits, food products have been used pedigree, pedigree gravy, bairo, purepet, chappi, drools, milk, biscuits, chappati and eggs. Vaccination provided to dogs by 10 in 1 vaccination for protecting them from several dangerous diseases. Reproduction and survival rate have been observed by monitoring them, domestication done by several people.

Result

Observation done on stray dog or also called indie dogs in our country India. During observation the total numbers of dogs observed were 135, and observation done on different localities of Lucknow such as Aliganj, Jankipuram Sector ‘F’, Atal Chauraha, Vikas Nagar, Indra Nagar Sector- 19, Gomti Nagar and Kapoor Thala, Isabella Thoburn College Lucknow. I had observed the behaviour of stray dog, observation done during period of 2 years from 13 March 2020 – 13 March 2022, stray who lived on road and stray who are adopted by people or domesticated by people, observation done by me mentioned below.

1. Nature of Dog: The behaviour of indie dogs was similar to non – indie dogs, as they are helpless so they choose or used to survive on the left-over places in cities or in small places left over near houses and where they can sit as there is no particular space for them. They eat whatever they get food in garbage or dump area as per observation.

1.1 Loyalty: -Dogs are very popular for their loyalty not sure if there are any other beings that are more loyal, but as compare to dogs they must be on the top of the list. I observed dogs are very loyal towards owner and those who gave them love; care and food, and I think it’s because of the combination of characters that make up who they are. They just want your love and in return, they will give you love and loyalty and much more in rest of their life as I noticed during my observation in their behaviour.

1.2 Unconditional love: - Dogs never care about the appearance of a human or their favourite person either you have any physically or mental disabilities. They don’t care if you have money or not. They are happy to love you for who you are. Even when things are going perfect, or even if you neglect them, they are just unconditional lovers they never stop loving you in any good and worst condition of your life. They will sense your pain and feel pain with you, even if you push them away from, they will always come back to you lick your face, love you try to make you happy always. I think this characteristic which I observe makes them unbelievable, and I admire them for that.

1.3 Inner and external peace of mind: -They are of simple and calm mind set from inner and as well outside. You will never see a dog obsess about how their tail appears, or their nose is too big or having too much hair or fur on their body. As we humans tend to stress over unnecessary things and dissatisfaction has an effect on person’s mentality.

1.4 Being Selfless: - dogs are simple minded but they are above all selfless creatures. They don’t really have any special demands from humans. They just satisfied with the basics needs; never expect something in return or a favour from humans. They never take away from you for their own benefits and because of these characters which make them a great companion of humans.

Cover Page

DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23>

- 1.5 The pups are more energetic than adult dogs, intelligent listen to command of a person while training them, experiment done on pups age 1 months using dog biscuit as treats for responding correct on command given to them, while its little bit hard to train an adult dog it takes around 2 months to train them with commands as pups should be trained between the age of 1 month to 5months we observed that pups easily catch the commands as compare to adult dogs.
2. **Behaviour of Dog when Come in Contact with Humans:** I had observed various changes during study in behaviour of an indie dog mentioned below-
 - 2.1 Observation done on dogs, when they come in contact with people who behave nicely with them the dog responds with wagging tail and jump up on person to show their happiness to human. Observations said that friendly towards people or well-behaved children who are friendly toward dog.
 - 2.2 Observed that the person and children who misbehaved with dog the dog shows stressful behaviour, tail under legs of dog shows its stress, while throwing stones on dogs then bark and ran away from the location and few shows anger towards that person.
 - 2.3 Experiment setup on dog1 with person 1 who is known towards dog very well or feeder of a dog wagged his tail, provided greeting to him and waited for him, person 2 with dog who is unknown to dog slightly wagged his or her tail and sat on ground, person 3 with the dog who is not friendly towards dog and tease the dog by beating and throwing stones on him, without harming them in response 90% of dogs afraid of that and ran away and 10% used to bark on that person then ran away from the setup applied (Table No.-2).
 - 2.4 Observation done on social places as mentioned in maps provided below, approx. 99% of dogs get afraid by speedy running vehicle near to them and 1% of dog bite in this state of action. They get afraid from this, people used to kick them on roads while they are sitting or sleeping on road side space available to them.
3. There are few deadly diseases from which dog suffers, human need to be aware of potentially deadly diseases that can strike the dog. We vaccinated around 50 dogs against these Diseases, the disease are Rabies, Canine Distemper, Fungal Infections, Leptospirosis, Heartworm Disease, Lyme Disease, Parvovirus, Bloat, Kidney Failure, Chocolate Poisoning and Cancer. We observe out of 2/10 dogs after vaccination, might having these disease symptoms and mostly parvo and canine distemper occur. The stray dogs reproduce twice a year, in one time they litter about 7 to 9 pups or 12 pups in one breeding season.
4. According to observation hardly 1 – 2 pups survive because of disease like parvo and distemper, due to lack of food and water and mostly in accidental case hit and run case usually approx. 1 -2 pups survive in a year, for controlling and managing population the government launch organization named HSI which sterilized dogs. for identification ear notch has been done on left ear of a dog, as limited population we easily cared them well but that's totally false mostly harassing, beating, killing of dogs or mass killing reducing number of dogs from society.
 - 4.1 Observing those dogs who get sterilized by government organization such as Humane Society International, those dogs get sterilized but also gaining unnecessary body weight which seems to be dangerous of their health and cause health issues such as heart attack.
 - 4.2 As survival of stray pup and dog are tough on streets, brave enough to adapt our environment and do not fall sick easily as compare to breeds dogs. In my observation 20% died because of diseases and 60% accidental death, 15% abusing dogs and 5% are natural death has been observed in these 2 years 13March 2020- 13 March 2022.
5. **FOOD PREFERENCE:** - The Stray dogs can eat almost anything and everything which they found to be eaten; they are all about survival so they are rarely picky eaters. Experiment done on feeding habit of dog and pups the food provided to them listed on (Table No.- 1) and mostly they loved to eat chapattis, diluted milk, pedigree, pure pet, drools, chappi, buns, bread, rice, chicken, fish, paneer, Parle G biscuits, oats biscuits, calcium bones and many more food they eat which is observed in 2 years from 13 March 2020- 13 march 2022 mostly preferred food is chapattis, milk, biscuits and pedigree in their daily routine.

Cover Page

DOI: http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23

Table No.- 1
Food Preference of Dogs of Different Locality in Gap Interval of 10 Days

S.No.	Location	No. of Dogs	Timing 1	Timing 2	Days	Dog Food	Chappati	Eggs	Bread and Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuits	Parle Biscuit
1.	Aliganj	10	5:00 AM	8:00 PM	1-10	Purepet	Chappati	Eggs	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	No	Eggs	Bun	No	No	Parle Biscuit
2.	Jankipuram Sector -F	20	4:30 AM	10:00 PM	1-10	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	No	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
5.	Atal Chauraha	15	5:30 AM	10:30 PM	1-10	Pedigree	Chappati	eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	No	No	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
6.	Vikas Nagar	05	5:00 AM	8:00 PM	1-10	Purepet	Chappati	Eggs	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	Chappati	No	Bread	Milk	No	Parle Biscuit
8.	Indira Nagar	10	4:30 AM	10:00 PM	1-10	chappi	Chappati	Eggs	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	No	No	Bun	No	No	Parle Biscuit
9.	Gomti Nagar	10	5:00 AM	8:00 PM	1-10	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
10.	Kapoorthala	05	5:30 AM	10:30 PM	1-10	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Pedigree	No	Eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
11.	IT College Lucknow	15	10:30 AM	2: 30 PM	1-10	Pedigree	Chappati	Eggs	Bread	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit
					After 10days	Chappati	chappati	Eggs	Bun	Milk	Oats Biscuit	Parle Biscuit

Table No. 2
Observation of Dog Behaviour on Different Locations with Different Person's

S.No.	Number of Dogs	Location	Person 1 Feeder (given food)	Person 2 Unknown (given food)	Person 3 unknown with bad behaviour
1.	Dog 1	Jankipuram Sector F	Wagged tail, greetings, licking, waiting for feeder.	Slightly wagged tail little bit afraid.	Afraid and bark and run away from the spot.
2.	Dog 2	Vikas Nagar	Wagging tail with greeting.	not wagged, afraid	Afraid, bark

Cover Page

DOI: http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23

3.	Dog 3	Indira Nagar	Wagging tail	Slightly wagged tail and sniff the person.	Continuous bark
4.	Dog 5	Gomtinagar	Wagging tail	Wagged tail and sniff the person.	Afraid and bark and run away from the spot.
5.	Dog 6	Kapoorthala	Wagging tail	Bark with wagging tail	Bark and run away
6	Dog 7	IT College	Wagging tail	Wagged tail and sniff the person.	Afraid and bark and run away from the spot.

DISCUSSION: The society see stray as a bane or manse for human environment or surrounding, in observation noticed that people see them as dirty creatures and see them as a disease transmission source to humans, like rabies instead of behaving this to them if we make them vaccinate there will be no issues occur rather than killing them of this issue, as in history it is stated that the connection between canine and humans is old since 1500years, no one else except humans start domesticating them for their personal demands [1]. The person see them as disease carrier, in my study resembles with as people only and only see them as a rabies carrier in society, which can be easily cure and treated by vaccinating them with anti-rabies [3]. As made them vaccinated 50+ stray dogs where I hadn't noticed any rabies case from these location in these 2 years of biting any human instead of this most human used to beat them, kill them brutally, through acids on them or rape them. The domesticated dogs are intelligent and they can understand more pointing cues [8]. In my study stray dogs and those strays which can't be domesticated both are having same intelligence and capable to understand the human pointing ways whether its food or any object they easily catch the gestures. They depend upon leftover food and beg to humans. Study found that stray dog survives on the food which has been thrown in the dump area or garbage area and some time when they saw human in shops or somewhere else, they imagine that this person provides them food [3]. As per study dogs communicate habitually with human where they get positive and negative both [22, 7]. In observation mostly 80% people used to beat them, poisoning them and their pups, harassment, throughing of acid on them and raping many more and in positive response only 20% of people shows love, care, respect towards them and feed them food.

About 63% early mortality life of stray is affected by humans, totally agree with this point during my study I observe that the life span decreases due to certain and bad activities of human as according to observation about 60 % death in accident due to lack of concentration in driving occur, 15% abusing dogs and 5% natural death humans are responsible for their mortality rate [16]. It is found that friendly and threatening signs through humans and they respond accordingly and observe that people used to feed them in different way because of biting fear and using point signals to guide dog to get his food to avoid direct interactions with strays. the observation done where I observe that while feeding to known dogs and new dogs, they hadn't bite me, those who are unfamiliar firstly scared of me after giving them food I do petting so very easily they feel comfortable with me [4]. The dogs have been used by human for their own benefit of health and wellbeing as according to study dogs are known for humans' best friend not for providing benefits, they are good companion, who always supports his master and specially children in home, provide mental peace and give positive environment to home and happiness [19]. Some researchers are agreeing to the point similar to study that after knowing them domesticating them in home a strong and lovable connection formed between stray dogs or canine with humans [13]. The connection to dog, may relieve in depression or high stress level or self-esteem, agree with their point dogs are stress reliever and companionship to them make life healthier and easier [14]. Owing pet provides positive environment. It also makes children responsible and provides support to them emotionally agreed to their point and bond provided among any animals but one of the strongest and most old bonds is human canine bond or relationship and used dog as stress reliever in children's disorders, named Animal Assisted Therapy, goal behind this to make strong bond to canine and children fearlessly. In study domesticated stray as well non, domesticated both helped me out to get relieve from stress [21, 6]. Pet dogs either those stray dogs to who are not domesticated, provide safety to the person who feed them, care, and love they are protective toward them too and provide better mental and physical health to a person [20]. It's not necessary that owning a dog make person physically fit there are many humans those having pets and they care for them still have obesity [5]. The study found that 30% people treat their pets as a stuffed toy and after domesticating them for 2 to 3 years, when their pleasure and enjoyment are over with the dog they left them on roads, tie them from trees in forest were noticed in study cruelty behaviour done by owners [2]. When someone misbehave done to dogs, and not taking care of them may lead to behavioural issues can be seen in dogs, such as barking and high anxiety level they might be suffer with shock or stress after neglected by family or abandoned noticed in study [11]. Observed behaviour issues occur due to negligence to dog, in study observed the same condition happened to one stray dog

Cover Page

DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23>

who has been domesticated by family who misbehave with him and tease him so he become aggressive, changed his environment and rather than giving him to any shelter made him readopt to a good person after living in free space and care taking owner his aggression ended up and lives lovingly with their new owner 2021 [18]. The aggression may occur due to misbehave to dog from owner or family member. Observed that during lockdown time in 2020 many owners misbehave with their pets as sort of thinking that COVID is spreading by them, and abandoned their pets on highways or forests and extra petting and care don't make dog more demanding they have their own needs too like as humans and there is no behavioural issue either getting dog from breeder and from shelter [17]. It was observed that before and after feeding to their master doesn't lead to their anger, but noticed that they see owner while eating hoping that owner will share his food to his pet no aggression is seen in 2 years of study. The study shows while scolding them for wrong work they make sad faces and feel quilted to their owner whether dog obey the commands or not [10, 9].

Conclusion: The society seems street dog as a dangerous creature, which is dirty and manse for humans and spreading diseases to them. As these live since many years in our society with humans and also known to be man's best friend either a breed dog or street dog both are of same nature and best companion for humans. Through the observation Behaviour of street dog is not dangerous towards any human, as observed in study usually the cases of biting are occurred just because of teasing, beating a dog sometimes killed to death for protection they bark or try to bite not intentionally. Several diseases some are deadly we never knew that dog suffering in pain sometime because of this unintentionally they bite and feel guilty without knowing their problem people use to abuse them beat them and poisoned them. Vaccination is one the solution to protect dog as well as human from rabies and other infections one vaccination safes two lives. So vaccinated around 100 dogs per year has been done with 10 in 1 vaccination. They feed on leftover food on streets many times because of spoilage food they develop worms in stomach in excess in numbers cause intestine rupture like parvo disease and many more, vaccination helps in preventing and by providing them the food which is good for their health observed less health issues, they also can be domesticated easily and they easily adapt the environment in compare to breed dogs. They are also a part of society they are our responsibility and called as community dogs. Rather than beating them feed them they won't bite, always provide love in returns to humans they are not manse in society they are important part of it. We should think more about it.

Reference

1. Aparna Srivastava (May 08 2020). Stray dogs are a social Responsibility- a Perspective. <https://www.strawindia.org/blogs/12/stray-dogs-are-a-social-responsibility-a-perspective.aspx>
2. Beverland, M. B., Farrelly, F., & Lim, E. A. C. (2008). Exploring the dark side of pet ownership: Status-and control-based pet consumption. *Journal of Business Research*, 61(5), 490-496.
3. Bhadra, A., and Bhadra, A. (2014). Preference for meat is not innate in dogs. *J. Ethol.* 32, 15–22. doi: 10.1007/s10164-013-0388-387
4. Bhattacharjee, D., Sau, S., and Bhadra, A. (2018). Free-ranging dogs understand human intentions and adjust their behavioral responses accordingly. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 6:232. doi: 10.3389/fevo.2018.00232 CrossRef Full Text | Google Scholar.
5. Brown, S. G., & Rhodes, R. E. (2006). Relationships among dog ownership and leisure-time walking in western Canadian adults. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 30(2),131-136.
6. Fawcett, N. R., & Gullone, E. (2001). Cute and cuddly and a whole lot more? A call for empirical investigation into the therapeutic benefits of human-animal interaction for children. *Behaviour Change*, 18(2), 124-133.
7. Gompper, M. E. (2015). *Free-Ranging Dogs and Wildlife Conservation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
8. Hare, B., and Tomasello, M. (1999). Domestic dogs (*Canis familiaris*) use human and conspecific social cues to locate hidden food. *J. Comp. Psychol.* 113, 173–177. doi: 10.1037/0735-7036.113.2.173
9. Horowitz, A. (2009). Disambiguating the “guilty look”: Salient prompts to a familiar dog behaviour. *Behavioural Processes*, 81(3), 447-452.
10. Jagoe, A., & Serpell, J. (1996). Owner characteristics and interactions and the prevalence of canine behavior problems. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 47, 31-42.
11. Kobelt, A. J., Hemsforth, P. H., Barnett, J. L., & Coleman, G. J. (2003). A survey of dog ownership in suburban Australia– Conditions and behavior problems. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 82, 137-148.
12. Liz Langley (January 17, 2020) Stray dogs have the natural ability to understand human gestures. <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/animals/article/stray-dogs-communication-rabies-health>
13. Marinelli, L., Adamelli, S., Normando, S., & Bono, G. (2007). Quality of life of the pet dog: Influence of owner and dog's characteristics. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 108(1-2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2006.11.018>
14. Martin & Farnum, F., & Farnum, J. (2002, October). Animal-assisted therapy for children with pervasive developmental disorders. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 24(6), 657-670.
15. Miklosi A. (2007). *Dog Behavior, Evolution, and Cognition*. Oxford University Press. pp. 95–136. doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199295852.001.0001. ISBN 978-0-19-929585-2.)

Cover Page

DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.08.23>

16. Paul, M., Sen Majumder, S., Sau, S., Nandi, A. K., and Bhadra, A. (2016). High early life mortality in free-ranging dogs is largely influenced by humans. *Sci. Rep.* 6:19641. doi: 10.1038/srep19641 PubMed Abstract | CrossRef Full Text | Google Scholar
17. Podberscek, A. L., & Serpell, J. A. (1997). Environmental influences on the expression of aggressive behavior in English Cocker Spaniels. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 52,215-227.
18. Salmon, M. D., Hutchison, J., Ruch-Gallie, R., Kogan, L., New, Jr., J. C., et al. (2000). Behavioral reasons for relinquishment of dogs and cats to 12 shelters. *Journal of Applied Animal Welfare Science*, 3(2), 93-106.
19. Schaffer, C. B. (2009). Animals connecting people to people: Insights into animal assisted therapy and animal-assisted activities. *Reflections*, 15(1) 42-45.
20. Siegel, J. M. (1990). Stressful life events and use of physician services and the elderly: The moderating role of pet ownership. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58(6), 1081-1086.
21. Van Houtte, B. A., & Jarvis, P. A. (1995). The role of pets in preadolescent psychosocial development. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 16, 463-479.
22. Vanak, A. T., and Gompper, M. E. (2009). Dogs canis familiaris as carnivores: their role and function in intraguild competition. *Mamm. Rev.* 39, 265–283. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2907.2009. 00148.x CrossRef Full Text | Google Scholar
23. Wang, X. and Tedford, R.H. (2008). *Dogs: Their Fossil Relatives and Evolutionary History*. Columbia University Press, New York. pp. 1–232. ISBN 978-0-231-13529-0. OCLC 502410693.)
24. Wayne, R. and Ostrander, E.A. (1999). "Origin, genetic diversity, and genome structure of the domestic dog". *BioEssays*. 21 (#3): 247–257. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1521-1878(199903)21:3<247::AID-BIES9>3.0.CO;2-Z. PMID 10333734. S2CID 5547543.)